

EOSC Denmark Coordination Forum
Activities and reflections 2026 (1)

Mandated Organisation
of the EOSC Association

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Danish e-Infrastructure (DeiC)

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1. Updates from the EOSC Association

The EOSC Federation now has the first wave of national and thematic nodes in operation.

List of pioneering EOSC Nodes¹

National nodes	Thematic Nodes	e-Infrastructure EOSC Nodes
EOSC Node Finland EOSC Node Germany EOSC Node Italy EOSC Node Poland EOSC Node SURF – The Netherlands	EOSC Node BBMRI-ERIC (health and food) EOSC Node Data Terra (environment) EOSC Node CERN (Physical Sciences & Engineering) EOSC Node European DTO (environment) EOSC Node Life Sciences Connect (health and food) EOSC Node PaNOSC (Physical Sciences & Engineering)	EOSC Node EUDAT

Additional to these first wave nodes, there is the EOSC EU Reference Node, which is describe below. With these initial nodes, users are invited to try out EOSC by searching for data and services to support their research aims.

The first wave has still to be seen as a very early stage for EOSC as the web of FAIR data and services. Especially for the thematic nodes we anticipate additional value for research whereas for the national nodes the frame seems to be primarily nationally oriented

For EOSC Association the first half of 2026 was dominated by preparations for the post-2027 governance and funding model of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). EOSC stakeholders including the EOSC Association and research organisations, stressed the need for:

- long-term funding certainty
- stable governance
- preservation of community trust
- avoidance of fragmentation between national and European infrastructures²

EOSC Association continued proceeding with the community-driven technical work anchored in five working groups with participation from the first wave nodes.

¹ <https://eosc.eu/building-the-eosc-federation>

² <https://eosc.eu/news/eosc-a-calls-for-a-distinct-work-programme-based-partnership-for-eosc-in-fp10>

**Proposed working groups not yet endorsed by the Node Coordinators Committee*

Source: <https://eosc.eu/building-the-eosc-federation/eosc-federation-build-up-group>

Additionally, to the working groups the EOSC-Association has several Task Forces, which have delivered reports on FAIR data implementation, semantic interoperability, digital preservation, health data integration with the European Health Data Space (EHDS), as well as data management and interoperability challenges across the federation. These reports are intended to guide the next phase of EOSC implementation and strengthen interoperability across national and thematic infrastructures.³

A major focus of the EOSC Association was the development of a common position on the future governance and financing of EOSC beyond the current Horizon Europe partnership period.

This year the EOSC Symposium 2026 will take place in Florence, Italy (14–16 October 2026).

2. Updates on EOSC in Denmark

Denmark continued preparation work on establishing a Danish EOSC Federation Node under the leadership of DeIC, which serves as Denmark's mandated member in the EOSC Association. The Danish node initiative aims to federate national research data, services and infrastructures into the wider EOSC Federation.

Denmark is active in EOSC governance structures through:

- Participation of the Danish Agency for Higher Education and Science in EOSC governance and policy discussions (EOSC Steering Group)
- DeIC's representation in the EOSC Association as mandated member for Denmark
- Participation in Horizon Europe EOSC projects and federation-building activities

³ <https://eosc.eu/news/eosc-task-forces-new-reports-strengthen-eosc-direction>

- On both ministerial and service provider level there are discussions on how the Nordic actors may participate collaboratively to support the build-up of EOSC

A Danish National EOSC Node charter (see p.8) will be a key framework for encouraging national engagement of the universities as well as the coordinating efforts and ensuring Danish research infrastructures can participate effectively in the European EOSC federation.

3. DeIC engagement in EOSC 2026

This section details completed EOSC projects with DeIC involvement in 2026.

EOSC4ALL

The core objective of EOSC4ALL is to create a truly inclusive and scalable European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Federation by making it easy, fast, and cost-efficient for organisations to deploy and operate EOSC Nodes. EOSC4ALL aims to make research move faster by lowering barriers to data and services across European borders. The project recognises that it is important to researchers, institutions and national e-Infrastructure provider organisations to make digital research environments easier to deploy, connect and adopt.

EOSC4ALL is a European initiative that focuses on secure digital research environments, including trusted access, file storing and sharing across borders. Built on the proven [SURF Research Cloud](#) approach, it offers a managed European model for secure research environments and collaboration between institutions and countries. For researchers, EOSC4ALL provides access to preconfigured, adaptable environments that reduce repetitive setup work and simplify collaboration. For institutional leaders, it supports research strategies through both technology and adoption activities that help engage stakeholders and turn plans into researcher uptake. For e-Infrastructure provider organisations, EOSC4ALL expands research service portfolios with technical capabilities and proven workshops that help European institutions identify stakeholders and accelerate adoption.

Current Status

The project has been granted funding and will start September 2026.

Looking Ahead

The EOSC4ALL project is expected to significantly expand the EOSC Federation by enabling a broader range of organisations to participate with much lower technical and operational barriers. This will help democratise access to research data and digital services, allowing researchers across Europe to collaborate more easily and work with shared resources across institutional and national boundaries. At the same time, the introduction of the digital research environment platform will simplify deployment processes and reduce costs, making it more feasible for smaller or less technically advanced organisations to join the EOSC Federation.

By strengthening interoperability, the project will connect diverse infrastructures into a more coherent and unified research environment, while core services such as AAI and national storage solution (EFSS) will ensure secure, seamless access and efficient data-sharing workflows across EOSC nodes. This will further reinforce the adoption of FAIR data principles, improving how research outputs are managed, discovered, and reused. In addition, EOSC4ALL contributes to strengthening European technological sovereignty by building robust, federated digital research infrastructures within Europe, based on national solution. Importantly, the project places strong emphasis on sustainability, ensuring that the developed services, platforms, and nodes can continue operating and evolving beyond the project's lifetime. Overall, these combined infrastructure impacts are expected to accelerate scientific discovery, foster innovation, and support a more integrated and data-driven European research landscape.

EOSC ENTRUST

European Network of Trusted Research Environments

ENTRUST aims to establish a European network of Trusted Research Environments (TREs) that enable the secure processing and analysis of sensitive data. The project addresses the growing need among researchers and public authorities to access confidential information while maintaining high standards of data protection. Building on existing TRE practices across Europe, ENTRUST is developing a common TRE Blueprint to support interoperability between countries, organisations, and research domains. In the long term, the initiative seeks to enable secure cross-border access to sensitive data and federated analysis through a shared legal, operational, and technical framework, unlocking the value of sensitive data across Europe.

Current Status

EOSC-ENTRUST has now entered its final year. DeiC continues to participate as a representative of Danish stakeholders and leads Task 4.6, Assessing the Adoption Level of the TRE Blueprint. During the project's second year, the TRE Blueprint has been successfully validated and further refined based on feedback and implementation experiences from year one.

Several key deliverables, including training packages and the Blueprint for Authentication, Authorization, Accounting, and Auditing Infrastructure (AAAI), are maturing and providing clear direction for future TRE implementation and governance.

Looking Ahead

The main challenge facing the project is ensuring the sustainability of activities and outcomes beyond the project's conclusion in 2027. An updated TRE survey is currently being circulated and will form the basis of the future TRE Provider Catalogue.

Danish stakeholders are encouraged to participate, as their contributions will help strengthen the European TRE ecosystem and support the continued development of interoperable secure research environments.

4. The EOSC EU Node and how to use it

The EOSC EU Node is Europe's first operational platform designed to support modern research workflows across disciplines and borders. It brings together data, tools, and services in one place, making it easier for researchers to collaborate, analyse data, and share results in line with FAIR and Open Science principles.

Rather than introducing new standalone infrastructure, the EOSC EU Node provides a single access point to a connected research environment.

Access: Researchers can log in using existing institutional credentials via eduGAIN, EU Login, or national eID solutions, with no need to create a new account. Once logged in, each user is given access rights based on their institutional role, ensuring that services and resources match their level of activity.

At the center of the platform is the User Space, a personal dashboard where research work can be managed end to end. From here, users can upload and process data, deploy tools, collaborate through shared workspaces, and monitor usage. Everything — from accessing services to managing resources — is handled in one place.

The EOSC EU Node operates with a simple credit system that makes access transparent and flexible. Researchers receive credits that can be used to run services such as virtual machines, interactive notebooks, and data transfer tools. Credits are automatically replenished, lowering the barrier to experimenting, collaborating, and scaling up research tasks.

A key strength of the platform is the range of integrated services supporting real research workflows. These include cloud storage and file sharing, interactive coding environments, scalable computing resources, and tools for transferring large datasets. Together, they enable researchers to move seamlessly from data access to analysis and sharing without switching between platforms.

Collaboration is built into the platform through shared Groups, where researchers can work together, share data and services, and coordinate projects. Groups allow teams to pool resources and ensure consistent access to tools, which is particularly valuable for distributed research teams working across institutions or countries.

For those new to the platform, training materials and guided learning paths are available, helping researchers move from basic navigation to designing and running complete workflows. This ensures that users can gradually build confidence and make full use of the available services.

Overall, the EOSC EU Node offers a practical, user-focused environment where researchers can find, access, combine, and reuse data and tools across Europe.

[Visit the EOSC EU Node here](#)

Access training materials here:

- [EOSC EU Node Learning Center on OpenPlato](#)
- [Getting started with the EOSC EU Node](#)

Please note: The EOSC EU Node is NOT suitable for any kind of sensitive data, rather solely for open data. Visit EOSC-EU-Node User Access Policy for information on legal compliance. For using the services, pay attention to potential legal issues and contact your university legal department with any questions.

5. Exploring the framework for a Danish National EOSC node

Denmark has strong digital research infrastructures and valuable institutional expertise. The question now is how these strengths can be connected more effectively — nationally and across Europe — in ways that create practical value for researchers and institutions alike.

DeiC is therefore preparing the groundwork for a project charter to support a future proposal for a Danish National EOSC Node (EOSC-DK). The intention is not to define a final model in advance, but to establish a shared framework for how relevant Danish digital research infrastructures — including data, tools, services, platforms and HPC resources — can be connected and represented within the evolving European Open Science Cloud ecosystem. This work builds on DeiC’s long-standing engagement with EOSC, drawing on nearly a decade of experience with EOSC-related developments and collaboration.

The immediate objective is to prepare a project charter that can:

- define the overall framework for EOSC-DK, including how infrastructures may be selected and prioritised;
- identify Danish infrastructures relevant for integration with the emerging EOSC Federation and existing EOSC Nodes;
- support stronger European coordination through governance models and sustainable funding approaches;
- promote shared ownership and transparent collaboration in order to reduce duplication, fragmentation, and siloed development;
- improve interoperability by encouraging alignment of standards and operational practices;
- explore transparent and sustainable cost-sharing approaches;
- and highlight national use cases that demonstrate concrete value for researchers and institutions.

To make the idea more concrete, an EOSC Node can be understood as a lightweight coordination and integration layer that connects existing resources rather than replacing them.

The illustration above shows how a node brings together different types of elements: research resources such as data, software, and publication repositories; generic resources such as HPC, cloud, storage, and research environments; operational functions that ensure coordination, security, and governance; and federating services that enable access, discovery, and interoperability. Together, these components form a connected ecosystem where existing infrastructures remain in place but become easier to discover, access, and combine across institutions and borders.

Broad dialogue is essential. Danish institutions have different needs, levels of maturity, and strategic considerations in relation to EOSC. A successful national node can only be developed through open discussion, shared prioritisation, and realistic expectations about where coordination is useful and where institutional autonomy should remain central.

If realised, EOSC-DK could give Danish researchers and institutions simpler access to shared digital research infrastructures through a more connected ecosystem of data, tools, services, and computing resources. Improved interoperability and coordination would help reduce duplication, support collaboration across institutions and borders, and increase the overall impact and efficiency of Danish research.

6. Future plans and reflections

Building on current developments, the EOSC Denmark Coordination Forum will focus on supporting practical uptake of EOSC as well as strategic positioning of EOSC-related activities in Denmark. While concrete implementations remain subject to institutional approvals, there is a clear direction towards strengthening both national coordination and European engagement.

Engagement in the EOSC Federation

With the first EOSC nodes now operational, efforts will focus on enabling Danish stakeholders to make informed and practical use of available services. This includes promoting awareness of the EOSC EU Node and related initiatives for initial engagement with EOSC, while ensuring clarity about their appropriate use.

In particular, the distinction between open and sensitive data remains essential. Platforms such as the EOSC EU Node are currently intended for open data, and any use of EOSC services must align with Danish legal requirements, including data protection and institutional compliance frameworks. Legal assessment therefore remains a prerequisite for adoption.

Progressing towards EOSC-DK

Work on a Danish National EOSC Node (EOSC-DK) will continue to mature, building on the proposed project charter and ongoing stakeholder dialogue. The ambition is to establish a coordinated framework that connects Danish infrastructures more effectively to each other and to the European EOSC ecosystem supporting researchers' workflows and service needs.

Future activities will focus on refining governance approaches, identifying relevant infrastructures, and developing concrete use cases that demonstrate value. Any implementation will depend on alignment with institutional priorities, sustainable funding models, and compliance with legal and regulatory requirements.

Sustaining and integrating project outcomes

As EOSC projects such as EOSC ENTRUST approach completion, attention will turn to how their results can be integrated into future activities. This includes the potential use of frameworks such as Trusted Research Environments (TREs), which supports secure handling of sensitive data, subject to national legal constraints and institutional decisions.

Supporting adoption and collaboration

Finally, continued emphasis will be placed on supporting adoption and contribution through communication and engagement with stakeholders nationally. By facilitating dialogue and shared understanding, we aim to ensure that Danish participation in EOSC develops in a way that is both practically useful and aligned with legal, organisational, and strategic considerations nationally.

In the recent evaluation of the DeIC Organisation a clear position for national EOSC engagement is stated as a national strategic ambition. Obviously, the pace for following this ambition will have to align with the build-up of a new DeIC organisation.

For now, focus is on moving from early-stage exploration towards more structured coordination and usage. This will be done with careful attention to legal compliance and institutional governance, ensuring that future EOSC-related developments are both feasible and anchored within the Danish research system with a clear value proposition.